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DELIVERABLE 1.1

HUMAN RECEPTORS MAP

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Coordinator's Organization Name: Universidade da Coruña

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WP4 Test and validation of the final device

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Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X

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Document information

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Lead Beneficiary	ICGEB		
Responsible Author	Tea Carletti		
Contributions from	Kirti Shila Sonkar, Alessandro Marcello, Ivan Coluzza.		

Background on FLUFET

Infectious zoonotic diseases that jump from animals to humans are on the rise, and the risk of a new pandemic is higher now than ever before. Future health models need to consider the close connection between human and animal health, and new technologies capable of continuously monitor places where the risk of pathogens transmission is higher (shared by animals and humans) are urgently needed to prevent the human, socio-political and economic cost from pandemics.

Continuous monitoring and harmonized data collection of animal farms are required by the European Parliament. However, current methods are not suitable for an in-situ, continuous and automatic detection, so today only a limited number of specific pathogens are monitored.

FLUFET will be the first automatized sensor able of continuously detecting a broad spectrum of viral targets, and with the unprecedented capability of detecting unknown viruses. This sensor will be based on graphene Field Effect Transistors (gFETs). FLUFET will detect infectious zoonotic threats before they spread to humans and create potential outbreaks, opening the door for a pandemic's prevention continuum. It will bring the possibility to incorporate the long-distance external factors heavily affecting human health at worldwide level.

FLUFET brings interesting opportunities for Health and pandemics experts and managers, Policymakers and regulatory/ standardization bodies, Animal farmers and their associations, Precision livestock farming solution providers, Investors and researchers in the multiple disciplines involved in the consortium.

FLUFET requires an interdisciplinary consortium including partners from computational biophysics, graphene technology, nanotechnology, sensing, microfluidics, virology, surface engineering and sensor design and electronics

Consortium Members

N°	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	UDC	Universidade da Coruña	ES	999629718
2	BEN	BCMaterials	FUNDACION BCMATERIALS - BASQUE CENTRE FOR MATERIALS, APPLICATIONS AND NANOSTRUCTURES	ES	928273511
3	BEN (IO)	INL	Laboratorio Iberico Internacional de Nanotecnología	PT	988145985
4	BEN	BIOMA	ASOCIACION CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION COOPERATIVA EN BIOMATERIALES- CIC biomaGUNE	ES	998347572
5	BEN (IO)	ICGEB	INTERNATIONAL CENTRE FOR GENETIC ENGINEERING AND BIOTECHNOLOGY	IT	999470444
6	BEN	GSEMI	GRAPHENEA SEMICONDUCTOR SL	ES	910983940
7	BEN	VTT	TEKNOLOGIAN TUTKIMUSKESKUS VTT OY	FI	932760440

History of Changes

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Comments	Contributor
1.0	26.08.2024	Draft	First Draft of D1.1		Tea Carletti Kirti Shila Sonkar
1.1	27.08.2024	Draft	Internal Review		Alessandro Marcello
1.2	27.08.2024	Final	Final version		Tea Carletti
1.3	11.02.2026	Reviewed	Reviewed	The virus-human receptors map has been reviewed to include ICTV Binomial Species Names	Tea Carletti

D1.1 – HUMAN RECEPTOR MAP. Map of the relationship between known viruses and their target human receptors.

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Viral infections pose a significant threat to global health, with frequent outbreaks and pandemics ([Abbey et al., 2020](#)). Pandemics caused by infectious zoonotic diseases, i.e. infectious disease caused by a pathogen that can jump from a non-human to a human host, are of concern. Factors such as deforestation and agricultural expansion increase the risk of zoonotic disease spillover by bringing humans and animals closer together. In the past few years numerous disease outbreaks have had suspected or confirmed zoonotic origin (e.g. Mpox, Ebola virus and COVID-19). Rapid and accurate detection of viral infections is crucial for effective disease management and prevention. The efforts at international levels to be prepared for another possible pandemic is huge. WHO, back in 2015, created the [WHO Research and Development \(R&D\) Blueprint](#), a global strategy and preparedness plan to accelerate the development of medical countermeasures when facing a new epidemic/pandemic. The WHO R&D Blueprint recently published the document “Pathogen Prioritization – A scientific framework for epidemic and pandemic research preparedness” ([WHO-R&DBlueprint, June 2024](#)), which rank a list of prioritized pathogens family, including *Disease X*, a term used to describe a currently unknown pathogen with pandemic potential ([WHO, 2018](#)). To complement this efforts, several other institutions are developing disease rankings at national and global levels, including the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) who created the [Priority Zoonotic Diseases Lists](#), facilitated by the U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, and the Coalition for Epidemic Preparedness Innovations (CEPI) who has partnered with the University of California, Davis, to expand [SpillOver](#), a platform that assess the pandemic potential of various viruses by considering environmental, host, and viral risk factors ([Jane Fieldhouse, 2024](#); [Kerlin, 2021](#)). Additionally, the [ZOVER](#) database integrates data from bat- and rodent-associated viruses (DBatVir and DRodVir) and includes up-to-date knowledge on mosquito- and tick-associated viruses, aiding in the surveillance and prediction of emerging infectious diseases ([Zhou et al., 2022](#)).

1.1.1. VIRUS RECEPTORS AND BIOSENSORS

Biosensors offer a promising approach to achieving rapid and accurate detection of viral infections, and virus receptors are key targets for their development ([Wan et al., 2020](#); [Kim et al., 2023](#)). Virus receptors are molecules on the surface of host cells recognized by viruses, facilitating entry and infection. For this purpose, viruses can also use co-receptors, accessory proteins, and different attachment factors, increasing the complexity of the relationship between virus-receptors. These receptors can be proteins, carbohydrates, or lipids, and their specificity and affinity for viral particles make them ideal targets for biosensor development ([Maginnis, 2018](#)).

1.1.2. CLASSIFICATION OF VIRUS RECEPTORS

Cellular receptors exploited by mammalian viruses can be classified into three main types based on their structure and function:

- **Glycoconjugates:** Including glycoproteins (e.g., sialic acid receptors for influenza virus) and glycolipids (e.g., Histo-blood group antigens (HBGA) on type 1, 2, and 3

GSLs for Human Norovirus (HuNoV), that serve as attachment sites for viral particles (Ayora-Talavera, 2018).

- **Proteinaceous receptors:** such as CD4 for HIV, which directly interact with viral particles (Matthias et al., 2010).
- **Polysaccharide receptors:** comprising carbohydrate molecules (e.g., heparan sulfate for HSV) that bind to viral particles (Itakura et al., 2020).

1.2. THE FLUFET PROJECT

The FLUFET project aims to create an automated sensing device capable of continuously detecting a broad spectrum of viral targets. To achieve this, a graphene field-effect transistor will be functionalized with human receptors that will recognize and bind viruses, sending an alarm to the system. Therefore, it is crucial to maintain an updated map of human receptors and their interactions with viruses. As shown in Figure 1, the number of articles describing novel virus-receptor interactions has been increasing since 2000, with approximately 29 new interactions described per year. Considering the constant increase in knowledge in this field, we set ourselves the goal of keeping this map up to date in the coming years and trying to assign a score based on the risk to human health.

Figure 1 – Annual discovery rates of distinct virus-receptor interactions, viruses, and host factors. Adapted from (Valero-Rello et al., 2024).

1.3. SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS OF VIRUS RECEPTORS

To build our map, we used the systematic analysis by Valero-Rello and colleagues (Valero-Rello et al., 2024), which considers all host factors promoting viral entry through direct interactions with viral particles. This includes:

- **Main receptors:** necessary and sufficient for viral entry.
- **Alternative receptors:** sufficient but not necessary for viral entry.
- **Co-receptors:** necessary but not sufficient.
- **Accessory receptors:** promoting entry but not necessary or sufficient.
- **Attachment factors:** moieties that promote initial virus binding.

The authors performed initial research on PubMed of mammalian virus names associated with keywords such as “receptor”, “attachment” and “binding”. The research gave 67492 results which were filtered through text mining and manual revision. Combining this initial research

with available databases ([ViralZone](#), [KEGG](#), [VTHunter](#)) and meta-analyses ([Zhang et al., 2019](#); [Wang et al., 2020](#); [Chen et al., 2022](#)), they obtained a final dataset of 210 cellular factors, 239 viral species, and 738 total interactions.

The table below summarizes the results they obtained classified according to the nature and role of the host factors involved.

Nature	Role	Total (Percentage)
Proteins	Main receptor	164 (22.2%)
	Alternative receptor	166 (22.5%)
	Co-receptor	79 (10.7%)
	Accessory receptor	207 (28.0%)
Moieties	Attachment	122 (16.5%)
Total		738 (100%)

Table 1 – Virus-receptor interactions classified according to the nature and role of the host factors involved. (Table from [Valero-Rello, Baeza-Delgado et al. 2024](#))

Interestingly, among the 738 virus-host interactions identified, 616 involved protein receptors, while 122 interactions were regulated by attachment molecules. Most of these moieties were sialic acids or other glycans such as heparan sulfate. Knowing the abundance on the cellular surface of such molecules, bound to proteins or lipids, this data suggests that there might be a significant number of yet unknown interactions between viruses and humans which are regulated by these surface molecules.

1.3.1. BROAD-SPECTRUM VIRUS DETECTION

From the 738 total interactions identified by Valero-Rello and colleagues it's evident how some receptors are used by many viruses. Examples include CD209, also known as DC-SIGN, which recognizes a variety of viruses from 13 different viral families and sialic acid, a sugar that can be found bound to proteins or surface lipids, which is used as an attachment molecules by several strains of influenza viruses as well as by other virus such as MERS or SARS-CoV-2. Considering the plasticity of some of these receptors we can speculate that these molecules could be useful targets for broad-spectrum viral detection because of their capacity to bind to multiple viruses.

1.4. MAP OF HUMAN RECEPTORS-VIRUS INTERACTION

The map we created consists of a list of all known virus-human receptors interactions, adapted from the work of Valero-Rello and colleagues.

The map is attached to this report as *Annex 1_Virus-Receptors Map and Ranking*.

In the table that we created it is indicated: name of the virus, ICTV Binomial Species Name, viral family, name of the receptors or family of receptor for which it has been proved an interaction with a specific virus, nature of the receptors (lipid, protein or sugar), role of the receptor in the interaction (main receptor, alternative receptor, co-receptor, accessory or attachment, as described in paragraph 1.3), name of the gene encoding the protein receptor and, finally, two different ranking systems of how risky the viruses listed in the map are for humans.

The first one, named “SpillOver Score” consist in the value assigned for that specific virus by the platform [SpillOver](#), described in introduction, which calculate the *risk score* of a virus taking in consideration several factors such as: host plasticity, if animal-to-human and human-to-human transmission has been proved for that virus, geography distribution of the host and other animals found infected, frequency of interaction between animals and humans in the host ecosystem, land use in host ecosystem, livestock and human population density in the host ecosystem, if the virus has already caused an epidemic or a pandemic and many other risk factors. We highlighted the risk score with a color scale where red correspond to the most dangerous virus and orange to the less dangerous. In grey are the viruses which are not reported in the SpillOver database. This ranking system consider the only zoonotic viruses.

The second ranking system we used is the one suggested by WHO in the most recent report of the R&D Blueprint “Pathogen Prioritization”. In this report they clearly indicate which family of viruses and pathogens are priority for WHO and so need to be investigated as well as diagnostic methods need to be developed in order to be prepared in case one of these pathogens may cause an epidemic or a pandemic. The approach of supporting research in the entire family, instead of focusing on a specific pathogen, helps mitigate the risk of missing potential pandemic pathogen. Here they rank the “Public Health Emergencies of International Concern (PHEICs) Risk” as High, Medium, Low-Medium and Low which we report in our table as color coded: Red, Orange, Light-Orange and Yellow respectively. In grey the viral families which are not listed as priority in the WHO report.

1.5. REFERENCES

- Abbey, E.J., Khalifa, B.A., Oduwale, M.O., Ayeh, S.K., Nudotor, R.D., Salia, E.L., Lasisi, O., Bennett, S., Yusuf, H.E., and Agwu, A.L. (2020). The Global Health Security Index is not predictive of coronavirus pandemic responses among Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development countries. *PloS one* 15, e0239398.
- Ayora-Talavera, G. (2018). Sialic acid receptors: Focus on their role in influenza infection. *Journal of Receptor, Ligand and Channel Research*, 1-11.
- Chen, D., Tan, C., Ding, P., Luo, L., Zhu, J., Jiang, X., Ou, Z., Ding, X., Lan, T., and Zhu, Y. (2022). VThunter: a database for single-cell screening of virus target cells in the animal kingdom. *Nucleic Acids Research* 50, D934-D942.
- Itakura, E., Chiba, M., Murata, T., and Matsuura, A. (2020). Heparan sulfate is a clearance receptor for aberrant extracellular proteins. *Journal of Cell Biology* 219.
- Jane Fieldhouse, D.W., Nistara Randhawa, Timothy Endy, Angel Desai (2024). *Eyes on Disease X: Ranking the Next Pandemic*. Sunbury Press, Inc.
- Kerlin, K. (2021). New Web App Ranks Spillover Risk for Newly Detected Viruses.
- Kim, E.R., Joe, C., Mitchell, R.J., and Gu, M.B. (2023). Biosensors for healthcare: Current and future perspectives. *Trends in Biotechnology* 41, 374-395.
- Maginnis, M.S. (2018). Virus–receptor interactions: the key to cellular invasion. *Journal of molecular biology* 430, 2590-2611.
- Matthias, L.J., Azimi, I., Tabrett, C.A., and Hogg, P.J. (2010). Reduced monomeric CD4 is the preferred receptor for HIV. *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 285, 40793-40799.
- Valero-Rello, A., Baeza-Delgado, C., Andreu-Moreno, I., and Sanjuán, R. (2024). Cellular receptors for mammalian viruses. *Plos Pathogens* 20, e1012021.
- Wan, Y., Shang, J., Graham, R., Baric, R.S., and Li, F. (2020). Receptor recognition by the novel coronavirus from Wuhan: an analysis based on decade-long structural studies of SARS coronavirus. *Journal of virology* 94, 10.1128/jvi. 00127-00120.
- Wang, W., Zhao, H., and Han, G.-Z. (2020). Host-virus arms races drive elevated adaptive evolution in viral receptors. *Journal of Virology* 94, 10.1128/jvi. 00684-00620.
- WHO. 2024, June. *Pathogen Prioritization – A scientific framework for epidemic and pandemic research preparedness*. <https://www.who.int/publications/m/item/pathogens-prioritization-a-scientific-framework-for-epidemic-and-pandemic-research-preparedness>
- Zhang, Z., Zhu, Z., Chen, W., Cai, Z., Xu, B., Tan, Z., Wu, A., Ge, X., Guo, X., and Tan, Z. (2019). Cell membrane proteins with high N-glycosylation, high expression and multiple interaction partners are preferred by mammalian viruses as receptors. *Bioinformatics* 35, 723-728.
- Zhou, S., Liu, B., Han, Y., Wang, Y., Chen, L., Wu, Z., and Yang, J. (2022). ZOVER: the database of zoonotic and vector-borne viruses. *Nucleic Acids Research* 50, D943-D949.

Virus	ICTV Binomial Species Name	Viral family	Receptor	Nature	Role	Genes	SpillOver Score	WHO pathogens prioritization
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	ACE2	protein	main	ACE2	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	GRM2	protein	accessory	GRM2	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	MYH9	protein	accessory	MYH9	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	NPC1	protein	accessory	NPC1	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	NRP1	protein	accessory	NRP1	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	SCARB1	protein	accessory	SCARB1	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	SDC4	protein	accessory	SDC4	97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		97,43	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 2	Betacoronavirus pandemicum	Coronaviridae	TMPRSS4	protein	accessory	TMPRSS4	97,43	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	AXL	protein	alternative	AXL	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	CLEC4G	protein	alternative	CLEC4G	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	DAG1	protein	main	DAG1	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	LAMP1	protein	coreceptor	LAMP1	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	SLC9A3	protein	accessory	SLC9A3	91,18	High
lassa mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lassaense	Arenaviridae	TYRO3	protein	alternative	TYRO3	91,18	High
latino mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus latinense	Arenaviridae	DAG1	protein	main	DAG1	91,18	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	CLEC10A	protein	alternative	CLEC10A	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	CLEC4G	protein	alternative	CLEC4G	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	FCN1	protein	accessory	FCN1	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	FOLR1	protein	alternative	FOLR1	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	HAVCR1	protein	main	HAVCR1	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGB1	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	MBL2	protein	accessory	MBL2	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	MERTK	protein	accessory	MERTK	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	NPC1	protein	coreceptor	NPC1	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	SIGLEC1	protein	alternative	SIGLEC1	87	High
zaire ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus zaireense	Filoviridae	TYRO3	protein	alternative	TYRO3	87	High
seoul orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus seoulense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGAV, ITGB3	86,49	High
nipah henipavirus	Henipavirus nipahense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB2	protein	main	EFNB2	86,48	High
nipah henipavirus	Henipavirus nipahense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB3	protein	alternative	EFNB3	86,48	High
nipah henipavirus	Henipavirus nipahense	Paramyxoviridae	MBL2	protein	accessory	MBL2	86,48	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	ASGR1	protein	accessory	ASGR1	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	FOLR1	protein	alternative	FOLR1	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1	85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		85,69	High
marburg marburgvirus	Marburgvirus marburgense	Filoviridae	MERTK	protein	accessory	MERTK	85,69	High
simian immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus simianimmunodeficientis	Retroviridae	CCR5	protein	coreceptor	CCR5	84,78	Medium
simian immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus simianimmunodeficientis	Retroviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209	84,78	Medium
simian immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus simianimmunodeficientis	Retroviridae	CD4	protein	main	CD4	84,78	Medium

simian immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus simianimmunodeficientis	Retroviridae	CXCR4	protein	coreceptor	CXCR4	84,78	Medium
simian immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus simianimmunodeficientis	Retroviridae	CXCR6	protein	coreceptor	CXCR6	84,78	Medium
simian immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus simianimmunodeficientis	Retroviridae	GPR15	protein	coreceptor	GPR15	84,78	Medium
rabies lyssavirus	Lyssavirus rabies	Rhabdoviridae	GRM2	protein	alternative	GRM2	84,69	Low
rabies lyssavirus	Lyssavirus rabies	Rhabdoviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGB1	84,69	Low
rabies lyssavirus	Lyssavirus rabies	Rhabdoviridae	NCAM1	protein	alternative	NCAM1	84,69	Low
rabies lyssavirus	Lyssavirus rabies	Rhabdoviridae	NGFR	protein	alternative	NGFR	84,69	Low
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	AXL	protein	alternative	AXL	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	CD164	protein	coreceptor	CD164	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	CLEC4G	protein	alternative	CLEC4G	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	DAG1	protein	main	DAG1	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	LAMP1	protein	coreceptor	LAMP1	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	SLC9A3	protein	accessory	SLC9A3	84,61	High
lymphocytic choriomeningitis mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus choriomeningitidis	Arenaviridae	TYRO3	protein	alternative	TYRO3	84,61	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 1	Sarbecovirus sarbecovirus	Coronaviridae	ACE2	protein	main	ACE2	83,14	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 1	Sarbecovirus sarbecovirus	Coronaviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209	83,14	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 1	Sarbecovirus sarbecovirus	Coronaviridae	CLEC4G	protein	accessory	CLEC4G	83,14	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 1	Sarbecovirus sarbecovirus	Coronaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M	83,14	High
severe acute respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus 1	Sarbecovirus sarbecovirus	Coronaviridae	TMPRSS2	protein	accessory	TMPRSS2	83,14	High
human coronavirus 229e	Duvinacovirus humanus 229E	Coronaviridae	ANPEP	protein	main	ANPEP	80,98	High
human coronavirus 229e	Duvinacovirus humanus 229E	Coronaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M	80,98	High
rousettus bat coronavirus hku9	Nobecovirus rousettusHKU9	Coronaviridae	HSPA5	protein	accessory	HSPA5	80,01	High
andes orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus andense	Hantaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1	78,81	High
andes orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus andense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3	78,81	High
andes orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus andense	Hantaviridae	PCDH1	protein	alternative	PCDH1	78,81	High
murine coronavirus	Embecovirus murinus	Coronaviridae	CEACAM1	protein	main	CEACAM1	78,62	High
murine coronavirus	Embecovirus murinus	Coronaviridae	cholesterol	lipid	attachment		78,62	High
murine coronavirus	Embecovirus murinus	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		78,62	High
puumala orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus puumalaense	Hantaviridae	CD55	protein	coreceptor	CD55	78,57	High
puumala orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus puumalaense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3	78,57	High
borna disease virus	Orthobornavirus bornaense	Bornaviridae	HSPA5	protein	accessory	HSPA5	77,21	Low
monkeypox virus	Orthobornavirus bornaense	Poxviridae	Glycosaminoglicans	sugar	attachment		76,14	High
sin nombre orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus sinnombreense	Hantaviridae	CD55	protein	coreceptor	CD55	73,36	High
sin nombre orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus sinnombreense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGB3	73,36	High
sin nombre orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus sinnombreense	Hantaviridae	PCDH1	protein	coreceptor	PCDH1	73,36	High
human mastadenovirus g	Mastadenovirus humanus G	Adenoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		73,23	Low-Medium
reston ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus restonense	Filoviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL	72,91	High
reston ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus restonense	Filoviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6	72,91	High
reston ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus restonense	Filoviridae	MERTK	protein	accessory	MERTK	72,91	High
reston ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus restonense	Filoviridae	TYRO3	protein	accessory	TYRO3	72,91	High
hendra henipavirus	Henipavirus hendrense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB2	protein	main	EFNB2	72,69	High
hendra henipavirus	Henipavirus hendrense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB3	protein	alternative	EFNB3	72,69	High
hendra henipavirus	Henipavirus hendrense	Paramyxoviridae	MBL2	protein	accessory	MBL2	72,69	High
human coronavirus hku1	Embecovirus humanus HKU1	Coronaviridae	HLA_complex	protein	accessory		72,46	High
human coronavirus hku1	Embecovirus humanus HKU1	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		72,46	High
dobrava-belgrade orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus dobravaense	Hantaviridae	CD55	protein	main	CD55	71,13	High
dobrava-belgrade orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus dobravaense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGB3	71,13	High
rotavirus a	Rotavirus rotavirusA	Reoviridae	F11R	protein	coreceptor	F11R	69,95	
rotavirus a	Rotavirus rotavirusA	Reoviridae	HBGAs	sugar	attachment		69,95	
rotavirus a	Rotavirus rotavirusA	Reoviridae	HSPA8	protein	accessory	HSPA8	69,95	

rotavirus a	Rotavirus rotavirusA	Reoviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGA2, ITGA4, ITGAV, ITGAX, ITGB1, ITGB2, ITGB3	69,95	
rotavirus a	Rotavirus rotavirusA	Reoviridae	OCLN	protein	accessory	OCLN	69,95	
rotavirus a	Rotavirus rotavirusA	Reoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		69,95	
african green monkey polyomavirus	Betapolyomavirus africanus	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		68,95	Low
rhinovirus c	Enterovirus humanus C	Picornaviridae	CDHR3	protein	main	CDHR3	68,08	Medium
tula orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus tulaense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGAV, ITGB1	67,93	High
middle east respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	Merbecovirus merbecovirus	Coronaviridae	CD9	protein	accessory	CD9	67,2	High
middle east respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	Merbecovirus merbecovirus	Coronaviridae	CEACAM5	protein	accessory	CEACAM5	67,2	High
middle east respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	Merbecovirus merbecovirus	Coronaviridae	DPP4	protein	main	DPP4	67,2	High
middle east respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	Merbecovirus merbecovirus	Coronaviridae	HSPA5	protein	accessory	HSPA5	67,2	High
middle east respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	Merbecovirus merbecovirus	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		67,2	High
middle east respiratory syndrome-related coronavirus	Merbecovirus merbecovirus	Coronaviridae	TMPRSS2	protein	accessory	TMPRSS2	67,2	High
hantaan orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus hantaanense	Hantaviridae	CD55	protein	coreceptor	CD55	66,13	High
hantaan orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus hantaanense	Hantaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1	66,13	High
hantaan orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus hantaanense	Hantaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		66,13	High
hantaan orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus hantaanense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	coreceptor	ITGB3	66,13	High
machupo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus machupoense	Arenaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1	65,82	High
machupo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus machupoense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC	65,82	High
measles morbillivirus	Morbillivirus measles	Paramyxoviridae	CD209	protein	coreceptor	CD209	65,79	High
measles morbillivirus	Morbillivirus measles	Paramyxoviridae	NECTIN4	protein	alternative	NECTIN4	65,79	High
measles morbillivirus	Morbillivirus measles	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1	65,79	High
guanarito mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus guanaritoense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC	65,35	High
orf virus	Parapoxvirus orf	Poxviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		65,34	High
macacine alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus macacinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	main	NECTIN1	64,23	Low
mason-pfizer monkey virus	Betaretrovirus masonpizeri	Retroviridae	SLC1A5	protein	main	SLC1A5	63,76	Medium
bat mastadenovirus a	Mastadenovirus vespertilionis A	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR	63,69	Low-Medium
whitewater arroyo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus whitewaterarroyense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC	63,68	High
Betapolyomavirus hominis	Betapolyomavirus hominis	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		63,24	Low
betacoronavirus 1	Embecovirus betacoronavirus1	Coronaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		62,29	High
betacoronavirus 1	Embecovirus betacoronavirus1	Coronaviridae	HLA_complex	protein	main		62,29	High
betacoronavirus 1	Embecovirus betacoronavirus1	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		62,29	High
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	CD9	protein	accessory	CD9	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	EGFR	protein	coreceptor	EGFR	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	FGFR1	protein	coreceptor	FGFR1	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	galactose	sugar	attachment		58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGA5, ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB3, ITGB5	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	KIAA0319L	protein	alternative	KIAA0319L	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	MET	protein	coreceptor	MET	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	PDGFRA	protein	alternative	PDGFRA	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	PDGFRB	protein	alternative	PDGFRB	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	RPSA	protein	main	RPSA	58,56	Low
adeno-associated dependoparvovirus a	Dependoparvovirus adenoassociatedA	Parvoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		58,56	Low
human coronavirus nl63	Setracovirus humanus NL63	Coronaviridae	ACE2	protein	main	ACE2	55,89	High
human coronavirus nl63	Setracovirus humanus NL63	Coronaviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209	55,89	High
human coronavirus nl63	Setracovirus humanus NL63	Coronaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	accessory	CLEC4M	55,89	High
human coronavirus nl63	Setracovirus humanus NL63	Coronaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		55,89	High
tyloncyteris bat coronavirus hku4	Merbecovirus tyloncyterishku4	Coronaviridae	DPP4	protein	main	DPP4	53,73	High
alphacoronavirus 1	Alphacoronavirus alphacoronavirus1	Coronaviridae	ANPEP	protein	main	ANPEP	52,88	High
alphacoronavirus 1	Alphacoronavirus alphacoronavirus1	Coronaviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209	52,88	High
alphacoronavirus 1	Alphacoronavirus alphacoronavirus1	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		52,88	High
alphapapillomavirus 10	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 10	Papillomaviridae	GPC1	protein	accessory	GPC1		Low

alphapapillomavirus 10	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 10	Papillomaviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1		Low
alphapapillomavirus 10	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 10	Papillomaviridae	SDC4	protein	accessory	SDC4		Low
alphapapillomavirus 7	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 7	Papillomaviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapapillomavirus 7	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 7	Papillomaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapapillomavirus 9	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 9	Papillomaviridae	ANXA2	protein	accessory	ANXA2		Low
alphapapillomavirus 9	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 9	Papillomaviridae	CD151	protein	accessory	CD151		Low
alphapapillomavirus 9	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 9	Papillomaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapapillomavirus 9	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 9	Papillomaviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGA6		Low
alphapapillomavirus 9	Alphapapillomavirus humanus 9	Papillomaviridae	Laminin_complex	protein	main			Low
alphapolyomavirus muris	Alphapolyomavirus muris	Polyomaviridae	Integrins	protein	coreceptor	ITGA4, ITGB1		Low
alphapolyomavirus muris	Alphapolyomavirus muris	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapolyomavirus nonihominis	Alphapolyomavirus nonihominis	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapolyomavirus quintihominis	Alphapolyomavirus quintihominis	Polyomaviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapolyomavirus quintihominis	Alphapolyomavirus quintihominis	Polyomaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapolyomavirus quintihominis	Alphapolyomavirus quintihominis	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
alphapolyomavirus terdecihominis	Alphapolyomavirus terdecihominis	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
argentinian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus juninense	Arenaviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		High
argentinian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus juninense	Arenaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
argentinian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus juninense	Arenaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1		High
argentinian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus juninense	Arenaviridae	SLC9A3	protein	accessory	SLC9A3		High
argentinian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus juninense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		High
argentinian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus juninense	Arenaviridae	VGCC_complex	protein	alternative			High
aura virus	Orthoflavivirus auraense	Togaviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		High
aura virus	Orthoflavivirus auraense	Togaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
avian coronavirus	Gammacoronavirus avium	Coronaviridae	ANPEP	protein	alternative	ANPEP		High
avian coronavirus	Gammacoronavirus avium	Coronaviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		High
avian coronavirus	Gammacoronavirus avium	Coronaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
avian coronavirus	Gammacoronavirus avium	Coronaviridae	HSPA4	protein	alternative	HSPA4		High
avian coronavirus	Gammacoronavirus avium	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
avian leukosis virus	Alpharetrovirus avium	Retroviridae	SLC9A1	protein	alternative	SLC9A1		Medium
avian metapneumovirus	Metapneumovirus avium	Pneumoviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGAV, ITGB1		Low-Medium
avian orthoavulavirus 1	Orthoavulavirus avium 1	Paramyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
bat calicivirus	Calicivirus vespertilio	Caliciviridae	HBGAs	sugar	attachment			
Betapolyomavirus macacae	Betapolyomavirus macacae	Polyomaviridae	HLA_complex	protein	main			Low
Betapolyomavirus macacae	Betapolyomavirus macacae	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
Betapolyomavirus secuohominis	Betapolyomavirus secuohominis	Polyomaviridae	HTR2A	protein	main	HTR2A		Low
Betapolyomavirus secuohominis	Betapolyomavirus secuohominis	Polyomaviridae	Lactoseries tetrasaccharide c	sugar	attachment			Low
Betapolyomavirus secuohominis	Betapolyomavirus secuohominis	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
bluetongue virus	Orbivirus bluetongue	Reoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			
bluetongue virus	Orbivirus bluetongue	Reoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			
bovine alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus bovinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
bovine alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus bovinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	main	NECTIN1		Low
bovine alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus bovinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN2	protein	alternative	NECTIN2		Low
bovine alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus bovinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	PVR	protein	alternative	PVR		Low
bovine alphaherpesvirus 5	Varicellovirus bovinealpha 5	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
bovine leukemia virus	Deltaretrovirus bovinus	Retroviridae	SLC7A1	protein	main	SLC7A1		Medium
bovine mastadenovirus b	Mastadenovirus bovinus B	Adenoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low-Medium
bovine nebovirus	Nebovirus bovinus	Caliciviridae	HBGAs	sugar	attachment			
bovine respirovirus 3	Respirovirus bovinus 3	Paramyxoviridae	cholesterol	lipid	attachment			High
bovine respirovirus 3	Respirovirus bovinus 3	Paramyxoviridae	EGFR	protein	main	EGFR		High
bovine torovirus	Torovirus bovinus	Tobaniviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			
brazilian mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus brasiliense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		High
bundibugyo ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus bundibugyoense	Filoviridae	NPC1	protein	main	NPC1		High
canid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus canidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
canine mastadenovirus a	Mastadenovirus caninus A	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Low-Medium
canine mastadenovirus a	Mastadenovirus caninus A	Adenoviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB5		Low-Medium

canine morbillivirus	Morbillivirus caninus	Paramyxoviridae	NECTIN4	protein	alternative	NECTIN4		High
canine morbillivirus	Morbillivirus caninus	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1		High
capuchin monkey hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus coerbensis	Hepadnaviridae	SLC10A1	protein	main	SLC10A1		Low
cardiovirus a	Cardiovirus a	Picornaviridae	ADAM9	protein	main	ADAM9		Medium
cardiovirus a	Cardiovirus a	Picornaviridae	VCAM1	protein	alternative	VCAM1		Medium
cardiovirus b	Cardiovirus b	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
cardiovirus b	Cardiovirus b	Picornaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Medium
carnivore amdoparvovirus 1	Amdoparvovirus carnivorosus 1	Parvoviridae	FCGR2A	protein	main	FCGR2A		Low
carnivore protoparvovirus 1	Protoparvovirus carnivoran 1	Parvoviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		Low
caviid betaherpesvirus 2	Caviid betaherpesvirus 2	Herpesviridae	PDGFRA	protein	main	PDGFRA		Low
cedar henipavirus	Henipavirus cedarinense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNA1	protein	alternative	EFNA1		High
cedar henipavirus	Henipavirus cedarinense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNA2	protein	alternative	EFNA2		High
cedar henipavirus	Henipavirus cedarinense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNA5	protein	alternative	EFNA5		High
cedar henipavirus	Henipavirus cedarinense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB1	protein	main	EFNB1		High
cedar henipavirus	Henipavirus cedarinense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB2	protein	alternative	EFNB2		High
cercopithecine alphaherpesvirus 2	Simplexvirus cercopithecinealpha 2	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	main	NECTIN1		Low
cetacean morbillivirus	Morbillivirus cetaceus	Paramyxoviridae	NECTIN4	protein	alternative	NECTIN4		High
cetacean morbillivirus	Morbillivirus cetaceus	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1		High
chapare mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus chaparense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	BSG	protein	alternative	BSG		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	HSPA4	protein	alternative	HSPA4		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	MXRA8	protein	main	MXRA8		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	PHB1	protein	accessory	PHB1		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	TIMD4	protein	accessory	TIMD4		High
chikungunya virus	Alphavirus chikungunya	Togaviridae	TSPAN9	protein	accessory	TSPAN9		High
chimpanzee adenovirus	Mastadenovirus troglodyti	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Low-Medium
coronavirus hku15	Deltacoronavirus hku15	Coronaviridae	ANPEP	protein	main	ANPEP		High
crimean-congo hemorrhagic fever orthonairovirus	Orthonairovirus crimeense	Nairoviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		High
dabie bandavirus	Bandavirus dabieense	Phenuiviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		High
dabie bandavirus	Bandavirus dabieense	Phenuiviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
dabie bandavirus	Bandavirus dabieense	Phenuiviridae	MYH9	protein	alternative	MYH9		High
deltaarterivirus hemfev	Deltaarterivirus hemfev	Arteriviridae	CD163	protein	coreceptor	CD163		
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	AXL	protein	main	AXL		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	CD300A	protein	accessory	CD300A		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	CLDN1	protein	accessory	CLDN1		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	CLEC5A	protein	accessory	CLEC5A		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	FCGR2A	protein	accessory	FCGR2A		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	HAVCR2	protein	alternative	HAVCR2		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	HSP90AA1	protein	alternative	HSP90AA1		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	HSPA4	protein	alternative	HSPA4		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	HSPA5	protein	accessory	HSPA5		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	LRP1	protein	main	LRP1		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	MRC1	protein	alternative	MRC1		High

dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	RPSA	protein	alternative	RPSA		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	TIMD4	protein	alternative	TIMD4		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	TYRO3	protein	alternative	TYRO3		High
dengue virus	Orthoflavivirus dengueense	Flaviviridae	VIM	protein	accessory	VIM		High
eastern equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus equidense orientale	Togaviridae	BSG	protein	accessory	BSG		High
eastern equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus equidense orientale	Togaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1		High
eastern equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus equidense orientale	Togaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
eastern equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus equidense orientale	Togaviridae	LRP8	protein	alternative	LRP8		High
eastern equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus equidense orientale	Togaviridae	VLDLR	protein	main	VLDLR		High
enterovirus a (non SCARB2-users: a2-6, a8, a10, a12)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	KREMEN1	protein	main	KREMEN1		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	ANXA2	protein	accessory	ANXA2		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	FN1	protein	accessory	FN1		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	HSP90AB1	protein	accessory	HSP90AB1		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	NCL	protein	accessory	NCL		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	PHB1	protein	accessory	PHB1		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	SCARB2	protein	main	SCARB2		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	SELPLG	protein	alternative	SELPLG		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	VIM	protein	alternative	VIM		Medium
enterovirus a (SCARB2-users: a7, A14, A16, A71)	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	WARS1	protein	alternative	WARS1		Medium
enterovirus b (CAR users: b1-6, swine vesicular disease virus)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	CD55	protein	coreceptor	CD55		Medium
enterovirus b (CAR users: b1-6, swine vesicular disease virus)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Medium
enterovirus b (CAR users: b1-6, swine vesicular disease virus)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus b (CD55 users: e3, e5-7, e11-13, e18-21, e24, e25, e29-e33)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	CD55	protein	accessory	CD55		Medium
enterovirus b (CD55 users: e3, e5-7, e11-13, e18-21, e24, e25, e29-e33)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	FCGRT	protein	alternative	FCGRT		Medium
enterovirus b (CD55 users: e3, e5-7, e11-13, e18-21, e24, e25, e29-e33)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus b (integrin users: a9, e1, e8, e9)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	FCGRT	protein	coreceptor	FCGRT		Medium
enterovirus b (integrin users: a9, e1, e8, e9)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus b (integrin users: a9, e1, e8, e9)	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGA2, ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB3, ITGB6		Medium
enterovirus c (no-poliovirus)	Enterovirus humanus C	Picornaviridae	CD55	protein	coreceptor	CD55		Medium
enterovirus c (no-poliovirus)	Enterovirus humanus C	Picornaviridae	ICAM1	protein	main	ICAM1		Medium
enterovirus c (no-poliovirus)	Enterovirus humanus C	Picornaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus c (poliovirus)	Enterovirus humanus C	Picornaviridae	PVR	protein	main	PVR		Medium
enterovirus c (poliovirus)	Enterovirus humanus C	Picornaviridae	TFRC	protein	alternative	TFRC		Medium
enterovirus d	Enterovirus humanus D	Picornaviridae	CD55	protein	main	CD55		Medium
enterovirus d	Enterovirus humanus D	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus d	Enterovirus humanus D	Picornaviridae	ICAM5	protein	alternative	ICAM5		Medium
enterovirus d	Enterovirus humanus D	Picornaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Medium
enterovirus d	Enterovirus humanus D	Picornaviridae	WARS1	protein	alternative	WARS1		Medium
equid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus equidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
equid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus equidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	HLA_complex	protein	main			Low
equid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus equidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGA4, ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB3		Low
equid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus equidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
equid alphaherpesvirus 4	Varicellovirus equidalpha 4	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
equid alphaherpesvirus 4	Varicellovirus equidalpha 4	Herpesviridae	HLA_complex	protein	main			Low
equid alphaherpesvirus 4	Varicellovirus equidalpha 4	Herpesviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGA4, ITGB1		Low
equine infectious anemia virus	Lentivirus equi	Retroviridae	TNFRSF14	protein	main	TNFRSF14		Medium
equine rhinitis a virus	Aphthovirus equine rhinitis A	Picornaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Medium
equine torovirus	Torovirus equinus	Tobnaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			
european brown hare syndrome virus	Lagovirus europaeus GII	Caliciviridae	O-Glycans	sugar	attachment			
feline calicivirus	Calicivirus felis	Caliciviridae	F11R	protein	main	F11R		
feline calicivirus	Calicivirus felis	Caliciviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			

feline immunodeficiency virus	Lentivirus felis	Retroviridae	TNFRSF4	protein	main	TNFRSF4		Medium
feline leukemia virus	Gammaretrovirus felis	Retroviridae	FLVCR1	protein	alternative	FLVCR1		Medium
feline leukemia virus	Gammaretrovirus felis	Retroviridae	FLVCR2	protein	alternative	FLVCR2		Medium
feline leukemia virus	Gammaretrovirus felis	Retroviridae	SLC19A1	protein	alternative	SLC19A1		Medium
feline leukemia virus	Gammaretrovirus felis	Retroviridae	SLC19A2	protein	main	SLC19A2		Medium
feline leukemia virus	Gammaretrovirus felis	Retroviridae	SLC20A1	protein	alternative	SLC20A1		Medium
feline leukemia virus	Gammaretrovirus felis	Retroviridae	SLC20A2	protein	alternative	SLC20A2		Medium
feline morbillivirus	Morbillivirus felis	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1		High
foot-and-mouth disease virus	Aphthovirus footandmouthdisease	Picornaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGAV, ITGB3, ITGB6, ITGB8		Medium
gallid alphaherpesvirus 2	Mardivirus gallidalph 2	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
getah virus	Alphavirus getahense	Togaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
getah virus	Alphavirus getahense	Togaviridae	MXRA8	protein	accessory	MXRA8		High
ghanaian bat henipavirus	Henipavirus ghanaense	Paramyxoviridae	EFNB2	protein	main	EFNB2		High
gibbon ape leukemia virus	Deltaretrovirus hylobatid	Retroviridae	SLC20A1	protein	main	SLC20A1		Medium
gibbon ape leukemia virus	Deltaretrovirus hylobatid	Retroviridae	SLC20A2	protein	alternative	SLC20A2		Medium
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	APOE	protein	accessory	APOE		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CD209	protein	coreceptor	CD209		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CD36	protein	coreceptor	CD36		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CD5	protein	coreceptor	CD5		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CD81	protein	coreceptor	CD81		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CLDN1	protein	coreceptor	CLDN1		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CLDN6	protein	coreceptor	CLDN6		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CLDN9	protein	coreceptor	CLDN9		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	CLEC4M	protein	coreceptor	CLEC4M		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	EGFR	protein	accessory	EGFR		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	EPHA2	protein	accessory	EPHA2		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	HRAS	protein	accessory	HRAS		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	Integrins	protein	coreceptor	ITGB1		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	LDLR	protein	alternative	LDLR		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	LY9	protein	accessory	LY9		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	NPC1	protein	coreceptor	NPC1		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	OCLN	protein	coreceptor	OCLN		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	PLSCR1	protein	accessory	PLSCR1		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	SCARB1	protein	coreceptor	SCARB1		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	SDC2	protein	accessory	SDC2		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	SDC4	protein	accessory	SDC4		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	TFRC	protein	accessory	TFRC		High
hepacivirus c	Hepacivirus humanus c	Flaviviridae	VLDLR	protein	alternative	VLDLR		High
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	ANXA5	protein	accessory	ANXA5		Low
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	ATP5F1B	protein	accessory	ATP5F1B		Low
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	EGFR	protein	coreceptor	EGFR		Low
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	FTL	protein	accessory	FTL		Low
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	GPC5	protein	accessory	GPC5		Low
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	SERPINB3	protein	accessory	SERPINB3		Low
hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus humanus	Hepadnaviridae	SLC10A1	protein	main	SLC10A1		Low
hepatovirus a	Hepatovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	GYP A	protein	accessory	GYP A		Medium
hepatovirus a	Hepatovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	main	HAVCR1		Medium
hom-1 vesivirus	Vesivirus hom-1	Caliciviridae	F11R	protein	main	F11R		
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	ANXA1	protein	accessory	ANXA1		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3, ITGB6, ITGB8		Low

human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	MAG	protein	alternative	MAG		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	MYH10	protein	alternative	MYH10		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	MYH9	protein	alternative	MYH9		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	main	NECTIN1		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN2	protein	alternative	NECTIN2		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	PILRA	protein	alternative	PILRA		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	SDC2	protein	accessory	SDC2		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus hominis 1	Herpesviridae	TNFRSF14	protein	alternative	TNFRSF14		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 2	Simplexvirus hominis 2	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
human alphaherpesvirus 2	Simplexvirus hominis 2	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	accessory	NECTIN1		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 2	Simplexvirus hominis 2	Herpesviridae	NECTIN2	protein	alternative	NECTIN2		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 2	Simplexvirus hominis 2	Herpesviridae	TNFRSF14	protein	alternative	TNFRSF14		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 3	Varicellovirus hominis 3	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
human alphaherpesvirus 3	Varicellovirus hominis 3	Herpesviridae	IDE	protein	accessory	IDE		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 3	Varicellovirus hominis 3	Herpesviridae	MAG	protein	alternative	MAG		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 3	Varicellovirus hominis 3	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	accessory	NECTIN1		Low
human alphaherpesvirus 3	Varicellovirus hominis 3	Herpesviridae	SIGLEC7	protein	main	SIGLEC7		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	ANPEP	protein	alternative	ANPEP		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	BSG	protein	accessory	BSG		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	CD46	protein	accessory	CD46		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	CD63	protein	coreceptor	CD63		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	EGFR	protein	coreceptor	EGFR		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	Integrins	protein	coreceptor	ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB3		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	NRP2	protein	alternative	NRP2		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	OR1411	protein	accessory	OR1411		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	PDGFRA	protein	main	PDGFRA		Low
human betaherpesvirus 5	Cytomegalovirus hominis	Herpesviridae	THY1	protein	alternative	THY1		Low
human betaherpesvirus 6a	Roseolovirus hominis 6A	Herpesviridae	CD46	protein	main	CD46		Low
human betaherpesvirus 6b	Roseolovirus hominis 6B	Herpesviridae	CD46	protein	alternative	CD46		Low
human betaherpesvirus 6b	Roseolovirus hominis 6B	Herpesviridae	NECTIN2	protein	alternative	NECTIN2		Low
human betaherpesvirus 6b	Roseolovirus hominis 6B	Herpesviridae	TNFRSF4	protein	main	TNFRSF4		Low
human betaherpesvirus 7	Roseolovirus hominis 7	Herpesviridae	CD4	protein	main	CD4		Low
human betaherpesvirus 7	Roseolovirus hominis 7	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
human gammaherpesvirus 4	Lymphocryptovirus hominis 4	Herpesviridae	CR1	protein	coreceptor	CR1		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 4	Lymphocryptovirus hominis 4	Herpesviridae	CR2	protein	alternative	CR2		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 4	Lymphocryptovirus hominis 4	Herpesviridae	EPHA2	protein	main	EPHA2		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 4	Lymphocryptovirus hominis 4	Herpesviridae	HLA_complex	protein	coreceptor			Low
human gammaherpesvirus 4	Lymphocryptovirus hominis 4	Herpesviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB6, ITGB8		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 4	Lymphocryptovirus hominis 4	Herpesviridae	NRP1	protein	accessory	NRP1		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	CD207	protein	coreceptor	CD207		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	EPHA2	protein	alternative	EPHA2		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	EPHA4	protein	alternative	EPHA4		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	EPHA5	protein	alternative	EPHA5		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	EPHA7	protein	alternative	EPHA7		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGA3, ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB3, ITGB5		Low
human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	PTK2	protein	accessory	PTK2		Low

human gammaherpesvirus 8	Rhadinovirus hominis 8	Herpesviridae	SLC7A11	protein	alternative	SLC7A11		Low
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	ACKR2	protein	coreceptor	ACKR2		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	ACKR3	protein	coreceptor	ACKR3		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	APLNR	protein	coreceptor	APLNR		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CCR2	protein	coreceptor	CCR2		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CCR3	protein	coreceptor	CCR3		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CCR5	protein	coreceptor	CCR5		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CD4	protein	main	CD4		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CLEC4M	protein	accessory	CLEC4M		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CXCR4	protein	coreceptor	CXCR4		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	CXCR6	protein	coreceptor	CXCR6		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGA4, ITGB7		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	M6PR	protein	alternative	M6PR		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	SDC2	protein	accessory	SDC2		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	SDC3	protein	accessory	SDC3		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	SDC4	protein	accessory	SDC4		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 1	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency1	Retroviridae	TIMD4	protein	accessory	TIMD4		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	ACKR2	protein	coreceptor	ACKR2		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CCR1	protein	coreceptor	CCR1		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CCR2	protein	coreceptor	CCR2		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CCR3	protein	coreceptor	CCR3		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CCR5	protein	coreceptor	CCR5		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CCR8	protein	coreceptor	CCR8		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CCRL2	protein	coreceptor	CCRL2		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CD4	protein	main	CD4		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CLEC4M	protein	coreceptor	CLEC4M		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CXCR4	protein	coreceptor	CXCR4		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	CXCR6	protein	coreceptor	CXCR6		Medium
human immunodeficiency virus 2	Lentivirus humanimmunodeficiency2	Retroviridae	GPR15	protein	coreceptor	GPR15		Medium
human mastadenovirus a	Mastadenovirus humanus A	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus b	Mastadenovirus humanus B	Adenoviridae	CD46	protein	main	CD46		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus b	Mastadenovirus humanus B	Adenoviridae	CD80	protein	alternative	CD80		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus b	Mastadenovirus humanus B	Adenoviridae	CD86	protein	alternative	CD86		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus c	Mastadenovirus humanus C	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus c	Mastadenovirus humanus C	Adenoviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAL, ITGAM, ITGAV, ITGB2, ITGB3, ITGB5		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus d	Mastadenovirus humanus D	Adenoviridae	CD46	protein	alternative	CD46		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus d	Mastadenovirus humanus D	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus d	Mastadenovirus humanus D	Adenoviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGAV, ITGB3		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus d	Mastadenovirus humanus D	Adenoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus e	Mastadenovirus humanus E	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR		Low-Medium
human mastadenovirus f	Mastadenovirus humanus F	Adenoviridae	CXADR	protein	accessory	CXADR		Low-Medium
human metapneumovirus	Metapneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		Low-Medium
human metapneumovirus	Metapneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	CLEC4M	protein	accessory	CLEC4M		Low-Medium
human metapneumovirus	Metapneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low-Medium
human metapneumovirus	Metapneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGA5, ITGB1		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	ANXA2	protein	accessory	ANXA2		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	CX3CR1	protein	main	CX3CR1		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	EGFR	protein	accessory	EGFR		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low-Medium

human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	ICAM1	protein	accessory	ICAM1		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	IGF1R	protein	coreceptor	IGF1R		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	NCL	protein	coreceptor	NCL		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	PRKCZ	protein	coreceptor	PRKCZ		Low-Medium
human orthopneumovirus	Orthopneumovirus humanus	Pneumoviridae	SFTPA1	protein	accessory	SFTPA1		Low-Medium
human orthorubulavirus 2	Orthorubulavirus hominis 2	Paramyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	ADAM17	protein	accessory	ADAM17		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	ANXA2	protein	accessory	ANXA2		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	CD151	protein	coreceptor	CD151		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	CD63	protein	accessory	CD63		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	CD81	protein	accessory	CD81		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	CD9	protein	accessory	CD9		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	EGFR	protein	coreceptor	EGFR		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	FGFR2	protein	coreceptor	FGFR2		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGA6		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	PPIB	protein	accessory	PPIB		Low
human papillomavirus	avirus humanus 9 (for HPV16 group, use genotype for prec	Papillomaviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1		Low
human polyomavirus 12	Deltapolyomavirus hominis 12	Polyomaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Low
human respirovirus 1	Respirovirus hominis 1	Paramyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
human respirovirus 3	Respirovirus hominis 3	Paramyxoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
human respirovirus 3	Respirovirus hominis 3	Paramyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	ACP2	protein	accessory	ACP2		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	ANXA5	protein	alternative	ANXA5		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	CACNA1C	protein	main	CACNA1C		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	CD207	protein	alternative	CD207		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	CEACAM6	protein	alternative	CEACAM6		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	EGFR	protein	accessory	EGFR		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	FFAR2	protein	accessory	FFAR2		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	HLA_complex	protein	alternative			High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	MRC1	protein	accessory	MRC1		High
influenza a virus	Alphainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
influenza b virus	Betainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	ACP2	protein	accessory	ACP2		High
influenza b virus	Betainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
influenza c virus	Gammainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
influenza d virus	Deltainfluenzavirus influenzae	Orthomyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
jaagsiekte sheep retrovirus	Betaretrovirus oviscaprinus 1	Retroviridae	HYAL2	protein	main	HYAL2		Medium
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	CLEC4G	protein	alternative	CLEC4G		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	HSPA5	protein	accessory	HSPA5		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	LMAN1	protein	accessory	LMAN1		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	PLVAP	protein	alternative	PLVAP		High
japanese encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus japonicense	Flaviviridae	VIM	protein	accessory	VIM		High
koala retrovirus	Gammaretrovirus phascolarctos	Retroviridae	SLC19A2	protein	main	SLC19A2		Medium
koala retrovirus	Gammaretrovirus phascolarctos	Retroviridae	SLC20A1	protein	alternative	SLC20A1		Medium
la crosse orthobunyavirus	Orthobunyavirus lacrosseense	Peribunyaviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		Low
lloviu cuevavirus	Cuevavirus lloviuense	Filoviridae	NPC1	protein	coreceptor	NPC1		High
lujo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lujoense	Arenaviridae	CD63	protein	coreceptor	CD63		High
lujo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lujoense	Arenaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High

lujo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lujoense	Arenaviridae	NPC1	protein	accessory	NPC1		High
lujo mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus lujoense	Arenaviridae	NRP2	protein	main	NRP2		High
mammalian orthoreovirus	Orthoreovirus mammalian	Reoviridae	F11R	protein	main	F11R		
mammalian orthoreovirus	Orthoreovirus mammalian	Reoviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGB1		
mammalian orthoreovirus	Orthoreovirus mammalian	Reoviridae	RTN4R	protein	alternative	RTN4R		
mammarenavirus lunkense	Mammarenavirus lunkense	Arenaviridae	CD164	protein	coreceptor	CD164		High
mayaro virus	Alphavirus mayaroense	Togaviridae	MXRA8	protein	main	MXRA8		High
mobala mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus mobalaense	Arenaviridae	DAG1	protein	main	DAG1		High
moloney murine sarcoma virus	Gammaretrovirus moloneyi	Retroviridae	SLC7A1	protein	main	SLC7A1		Medium
mouse mammary tumor virus	Betaretrovirus murinus	Retroviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		Medium
mumps orthorubulavirus	Orthorubulavirus mumps	Paramyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
murid betaherpesvirus 1	Muromegalovirus muridbeta 1	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
murid gammaherpesvirus 4	Muromicrovirus muridgamma 4	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
murine leukemia virus (SLC-users: amphotropic, ecotropic, moloney)	Gammaretrovirus murinus	Retroviridae	SLC20A1	protein	alternative	SLC20A1		Medium
murine leukemia virus (SLC-users: amphotropic, ecotropic, moloney)	Gammaretrovirus murinus	Retroviridae	SLC20A2	protein	alternative	SLC20A2		Medium
murine leukemia virus (SLC-users: amphotropic, ecotropic, moloney)	Gammaretrovirus murinus	Retroviridae	SLC7A1	protein	main	SLC7A1		Medium
murine leukemia virus (XPR1 users: polytropic, xenotropic)	Gammaretrovirus murinus	Retroviridae	XPR1	protein	main	XPR1		Medium
murine respirovirus	Respirovirus murinus	Paramyxoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			High
murine rotavirus	Rotavirus murinus	Reoviridae	HSPA8	protein	accessory	HSPA8		
murine rotavirus	Rotavirus murinus	Reoviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3		
murine rotavirus	Rotavirus murinus	Reoviridae	P4HB	protein	accessory	P4HB		
murray valley encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus murrayvalleyense	Flaviviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
myxoma virus	Leporipoxvirus myxomatosis	Poxviridae	CCR1	protein	alternative	CCR1		High
myxoma virus	Leporipoxvirus myxomatosis	Poxviridae	CCR5	protein	alternative	CCR5		High
myxoma virus	Leporipoxvirus myxomatosis	Poxviridae	CXCR4	protein	main	CXCR4		High
new york hantavirus	Orthohantavirus newyorkense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGB3		High
norwalk virus (murine norovirus)	Norovirus murinus / Norovirus norwalk	Caliciviridae	CD300LD	protein	alternative	CD300LD		
norwalk virus (murine norovirus)	Norovirus murinus / Norovirus norwalk	Caliciviridae	CD300LF	protein	main	CD300LF		
norwalk virus (murine norovirus)	Norovirus murinus / Norovirus norwalk	Caliciviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			
norwalk virus (norwalkvirus)	Norovirus norwalkense	Caliciviridae	HBGAs	sugar	attachment			
oliveros mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus oliverosense	Arenaviridae	DAG1	protein	main	DAG1		High
onyong-nyong virus	Alphavirus onyongnyongense	Togaviridae	MXRA8	protein	main	MXRA8		High
oropouche orthobunyavirus	Orthobunyavirus oropouchense	Peribunyaviridae	LRP1	protein	main	LRP1		Low
orthohantavirus maporalense	Orthohantavirus maporalense	Hantaviridae	PCDH1	protein	main	PCDH1		High
ovine enzootic nasal tumor virus	Betaretrovirus oviscaprinus 2	Retroviridae	HYAL2	protein	main	HYAL2		Medium
pangolin coronavirus	Sarbecovirus pangolin	Coronaviridae	ACE2	protein	main	ACE2		High
parechovirus a	Parechovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Medium
parechovirus a	Parechovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGAV, ITGB1, ITGB3, ITGB6		Medium
pestivirus a	Pestivirus bovinus 1	Flaviviridae	CD46	protein	main	CD46		High
pestivirus b	Pestivirus bovinus 2	Flaviviridae	CD46	protein	main	CD46		High
pestivirus c	Pestivirus suid 1	Flaviviridae	RPSA	protein	accessory	RPSA		High
pestivirus h	Pestivirus hobiense	Flaviviridae	CD46	protein	main	CD46		High
pestivirus k	Pestivirus porcinius 2	Flaviviridae	CD46	protein	main	CD46		High
phocine morbillivirus	Morbillivirus phocinus	Paramyxoviridae	HBEGF	protein	alternative	HBEGF		High
phocine morbillivirus	Morbillivirus phocinus	Paramyxoviridae	NECTIN4	protein	alternative	NECTIN4		High
phocine morbillivirus	Morbillivirus phocinus	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1		High
porcine circovirus 2	Circovirus porcinius 2	Circoviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			
porcine circovirus 2	Circovirus porcinius 2	Circoviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	ANPEP	protein	accessory	ANPEP		High
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		High
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	cholesterol	lipid	attachment			High
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3		High
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	OCLN	protein	accessory	OCLN		High

porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		High
porcine epidemic diarrhea virus	Alphacoronavirus suidae 1	Coronaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC	High
porcine mastadenovirus b	Mastadenovirus porcinus B	Adenoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		Low-Medium
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	CD163	protein	main	CD163	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	cholesterol	lipid	attachment		
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	EGFR	protein	accessory	EGFR	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	HSPA8	protein	coreceptor	HSPA8	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	MYH9	protein	coreceptor	MYH9	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	SDC4	protein	accessory	SDC4	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	SIGLEC1	protein	coreceptor	SIGLEC1	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	SIGLEC10	protein	coreceptor	SIGLEC10	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	TIMD4	protein	accessory	TIMD4	
porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome virus	Betaarterivirus suid 1 / Betaarterivirus suid 2	Arteriviridae	VIM	protein	accessory	VIM	
porcine torovirus	Torovirus porcinus	Tobnaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		
primate erythroparvovirus 1	Erythroparvovirus primatus 1	Parvoviridae	Glycosphingolipid	sugar	attachment		Low
primate erythroparvovirus 1	Erythroparvovirus primatus 1	Parvoviridae	Integrins	protein	main	ITGA5, ITGB1	Low
primate erythroparvovirus 1	Erythroparvovirus primatus 1	Parvoviridae	XRCC5	protein	coreceptor	XRCC5	Low
primate t-lymphotropic virus 1	Deltaretrovirus primatus 1	Retroviridae	NRP1	protein	coreceptor	NRP1	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 1	Deltaretrovirus primatus 1	Retroviridae	SDC1	protein	accessory	SDC1	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 1	Deltaretrovirus primatus 1	Retroviridae	SDC2	protein	accessory	SDC2	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 1	Deltaretrovirus primatus 1	Retroviridae	SDC3	protein	accessory	SDC3	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 1	Deltaretrovirus primatus 1	Retroviridae	SDC4	protein	accessory	SDC4	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 1	Deltaretrovirus primatus 1	Retroviridae	SLC2A1	protein	main	SLC2A1	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 2	Deltaretrovirus primatus 2	Retroviridae	NRP1	protein	coreceptor	NRP1	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 2	Deltaretrovirus primatus 2	Retroviridae	SLC2A1	protein	coreceptor	SLC2A1	Medium
primate t-lymphotropic virus 3	Deltaretrovirus primatus 3	Retroviridae	SLC2A1	protein	main	SLC2A1	Medium
prospect hill orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus prospecthillense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB1	High
prospect hill orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus prospecthillense	Hantaviridae	PCDH1	protein	main	PCDH1	High
puma lentivirus	Lentivirus concolor	Retroviridae	TNFRSF4	protein	accessory	TNFRSF4	Medium
punta toro phlebovirus	Phlebovirus puntatorensis	Phenuiviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209	High
rabbit hemorrhagic disease virus	Lagovirus europaeus GI	Caliciviridae	HBGAs	sugar	attachment		
rabbit vesivirus	Vesivirus leporinus	Caliciviridae	ANXA2	protein	accessory	ANXA2	
rd114 retrovirus	Gammaretrovirus feliformis	Retroviridae	SLC1A5	protein	main	SLC1A5	Medium
recovirus a	Recovirus A	Caliciviridae	HBGAs	sugar	attachment		
rhesus macaque recovirus	Recovirus macacae	Caliciviridae	CXADR	protein	main	CXADR	
rhinovirus a	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	ICAM1	protein	main	ICAM1	Medium
rhinovirus a	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	LDLR	protein	alternative	LDLR	Medium
rhinovirus a	Enterovirus humanus A	Picornaviridae	VLDLR	protein	alternative	VLDLR	Medium
rhinovirus b	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment		Medium
rhinovirus b	Enterovirus humanus B	Picornaviridae	ICAM1	protein	main	ICAM1	Medium
rift valley fever phlebovirus	Phlebovirus riftvalleyensis	Phenuiviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209	High
rift valley fever phlebovirus	Phlebovirus riftvalleyensis	Phenuiviridae	CLEC4M	protein	accessory	CLEC4M	High
rift valley fever phlebovirus	Phlebovirus riftvalleyensis	Phenuiviridae	LRP1	protein	accessory	LRP1	High
rinderpest morbillivirus	Morbillivirus rinderpestis	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1	High
rodent hepacivirus	Hepacivirus rodens	Flaviviridae	SCARB1	protein	main	SCARB1	High
rodent protoparvovirus 1	Protoparvovirus rodens 1	Parvoviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment		Low
ross river virus	Alphavirus rossriverense	Togaviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6	High
ross river virus	Alphavirus rossriverense	Togaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1	High
ross river virus	Alphavirus rossriverense	Togaviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGA1, ITGB1	High
ross river virus	Alphavirus rossriverense	Togaviridae	MXRA8	protein	main	MXRA8	High
ross river virus	Alphavirus rossriverense	Togaviridae	SLC1A5	protein	accessory	SLC1A5	High
rubivirus rubellae	Rubivirus rubellae	Matonaviridae	MOG	protein	main	MOG	
saimiriine alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus saimiriinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	alternative	NECTIN1	Low

saimiriine alphaherpesvirus 1	Simplexvirus saimiriinealpha 1	Herpesviridae	PVR	protein	main	PVR		Low
saimiriine gammaherpesvirus 2	Rhadinovirus saimiriinegamma 2	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
sangassou orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus sangassouense	Hantaviridae	CD55	protein	main	CD55		High
sangassou orthohantavirus	Orthohantavirus sangassouense	Hantaviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGB1		High
sapelovirus a	Sapelovirus suid 1	Picornaviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			Medium
sapporo virus	Sapovirus sapporo	Caliciviridae	sialic_acids	sugar	attachment			
sars-like coronavirus wiv16	Sarbecovirus sarbecovirus	Coronaviridae	ACE2	protein	main	ACE2		High
semliki forest virus	Alphavirus semliki forestense	Togaviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		High
semliki forest virus	Alphavirus semliki forestense	Togaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	accessory	CLEC4M		High
semliki forest virus	Alphavirus semliki forestense	Togaviridae	LRP8	protein	alternative	LRP8		High
semliki forest virus	Alphavirus semliki forestense	Togaviridae	MXRA8	protein	accessory	MXRA8		High
semliki forest virus	Alphavirus semliki forestense	Togaviridae	VLDLR	protein	alternative	VLDLR		High
senecavirus a	Senecavirus a	Picornaviridae	ANTXR1	protein	main	ANTXR1		Medium
senecavirus a	Senecavirus a	Picornaviridae	cholesterol	lipid	attachment			Medium
serra do navio mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus doNavioense	Arenaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	main	HAVCR1		High
serra do navio mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus doNavioense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		
simian retrovirus 5	Betaretrovirus simian 5	Retroviridae	SLC1A5	protein	main	SLC1A5		Medium
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	BSG	protein	alternative	BSG		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	FUZ	protein	accessory	FUZ		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	LRP8	protein	alternative	LRP8		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	RPSA	protein	alternative	RPSA		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	SLC11A2	protein	main	SLC11A2		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	TSPAN9	protein	accessory	TSPAN9		High
sindbis virus	Alphavirus sindbis	Togaviridae	VLDLR	protein	alternative	VLDLR		High
small ruminant morbillivirus	Morbillivirus smallruminantis	Paramyxoviridae	NECTIN4	protein	alternative	NECTIN4		High
small ruminant morbillivirus	Morbillivirus smallruminantis	Paramyxoviridae	SLAMF1	protein	main	SLAMF1		High
sudan ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus sudanense	Filoviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL		High
sudan ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus sudanense	Filoviridae	ERBB2	protein	accessory	ERBB2		High
sudan ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus sudanense	Filoviridae	HAVCR1	protein	main	HAVCR1		High
sudan ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus sudanense	Filoviridae	NPC1	protein	coreceptor	NPC1		High
suid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus suidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			Low
suid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus suidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN1	protein	alternative	NECTIN1		Low
suid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus suidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	NECTIN2	protein	alternative	NECTIN2		Low
suid alphaherpesvirus 1	Varicellovirus suidalpha 1	Herpesviridae	PVR	protein	main	PVR		Low
swine acute diarrhoea syndrome coronavirus	Alphacoronavirus swineacutediarrheasyndrome	Coronaviridae	PPIB	protein	accessory	PPIB		High
swine acute diarrhoea syndrome coronavirus	Alphacoronavirus swineacutediarrheasyndrome	Coronaviridae	VIM	protein	accessory	VIM		High
tacaribe mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus tacaribeense	Arenaviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1		High
tacaribe mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus tacaribeense	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		High
tai forest ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus taiforestense	Filoviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL		High
tai forest ebolavirus	Orthoebolavirus taiforestense	Filoviridae	CLEC10A	protein	accessory	CLEC10A		High
tamiami mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus tamiamiensis	Arenaviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
tamiami mammarenavirus	Mammarenavirus tamiamiensis	Arenaviridae	TFRC	protein	main	TFRC		High
tembusu virus	Orthoflavivirus tembusuense	Flaviviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
tembusu virus	Orthoflavivirus tembusuense	Flaviviridae	HSPA5	protein	main	HSPA5		High
tembusu virus	Orthoflavivirus tembusuense	Flaviviridae	HSPA9	protein	accessory	HSPA9		High
tick-borne encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus encephalitis	Flaviviridae	cholesterol	lipid	attachment			High
tick-borne encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus encephalitis	Flaviviridae	HAVCR1	protein	main	HAVCR1		High
tick-borne encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus encephalitis	Flaviviridae	LRP8	protein	main	LRP8		High

tick-borne encephalitis virus	Orthoflavivirus encephalitis	Flaviviridae	RPSA	protein	alternative	RPSA		High
toscana phlebovirus	Phlebovirus toscanaense	Phenuiviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		High
toscana phlebovirus	Phlebovirus toscanaense	Phenuiviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
ungulate bocaparvovirus 1	Bocaparvovirus unguatus 1	Parvoviridae	GYP A	protein	accessory	GYP A		Low
usutu virus	Orthoflavivirus usutense	Flaviviridae	CD207	protein	main	CD207		High
usutu virus	Orthoflavivirus usutense	Flaviviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3		High
uukuniemi uukuvirus	Uukuvirus uukuniemi	Phenuiviridae	CD209	protein	main	CD209		High
uukuniemi uukuvirus	Uukuvirus uukuniemi	Phenuiviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	AXL	protein	accessory	AXL		High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	GAS6	protein	accessory	GAS6		High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	Integrins	protein	alternative	ITGB1		High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	Laminin_complex	protein	alternative			High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	MARCO	protein	accessory	MARCO		High
vaccinia virus	Orthopoxvirus vaccinia	Poxviridae	SLC3A2	protein	main	SLC3A2		High
venezuelan equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus venezuelanequineencephalitisense	Togaviridae	LDLRAD3	protein	alternative	LDLRAD3		High
venezuelan equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus venezuelanequineencephalitisense	Togaviridae	RPSA	protein	main	RPSA		High
vesicular stomatitis virus	Vesiculovirus vesicularstomatitis	Rhabdoviridae	LDLR	protein	main	LDLR		Low
vesicular stomatitis virus	Vesiculovirus vesicularstomatitis	Rhabdoviridae	MSR1	protein	accessory	MSR1		Low
visna-maedi virus	Lentivirus ovicaprinus	Retroviridae	CD4	protein	accessory	CD4		Medium
visna-maedi virus	Lentivirus ovicaprinus	Retroviridae	chondroitin_S_dermatan_S	sugar	attachment			Medium
visna-maedi virus	Lentivirus ovicaprinus	Retroviridae	CXCR4	protein	accessory	CXCR4		Medium
visna-maedi virus	Lentivirus ovicaprinus	Retroviridae	MRC1	protein	main	MRC1		Medium
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	CD207	protein	alternative	CD207		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	CD209	protein	accessory	CD209		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	CD300A	protein	accessory	CD300A		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	CLEC4M	protein	main	CLEC4M		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	ICAM1	protein	alternative	ICAM1		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB3		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	MBL2	protein	accessory	MBL2		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	RPSA	protein	accessory	RPSA		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	TIMD4	protein	accessory	TIMD4		High
west nile virus	Orthoflavivirus westnileense	Flaviviridae	VCP	protein	accessory	VCP		High
western equine encephalitis virus	Alphavirus equidense occidentale	Togaviridae	BSG	protein	accessory	BSG		High
woolly monkey hepatitis b virus	Orthohepadnavirus lanigeri	Hepadnaviridae	SLC10A1	protein	main	SLC10A1		Low
yellow fever virus	Orthoflavivirus yellowfeverense	Flaviviridae	CD300A	protein	accessory	CD300A		High
yellow fever virus	Orthoflavivirus yellowfeverense	Flaviviridae	GRK2	protein	accessory	GRK2		High
yellow fever virus	Orthoflavivirus yellowfeverense	Flaviviridae	HAVCR1	protein	accessory	HAVCR1		High
yellow fever virus	Orthoflavivirus yellowfeverense	Flaviviridae	heparan_S_Heparin	sugar	attachment			High
yellow fever virus	Orthoflavivirus yellowfeverense	Flaviviridae	TIMD4	protein	accessory	TIMD4		High
Yellow Fever Virus	Orthoflavivirus yellowfeverense	Flaviviridae	LRP4	protein				High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	AXL	protein	alternative	AXL		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	CD209	protein	alternative	CD209		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	CLEC4M	protein	alternative	CLEC4M		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	EGFR	protein	accessory	EGFR		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	HAVCR1	protein	alternative	HAVCR1		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	Integrins	protein	accessory	ITGAV, ITGB5		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	SCARB1	protein	alternative	SCARB1		High
zika virus	Orthoflavivirus zikaense	Flaviviridae	TYRO3	protein	alternative	TYRO3		High